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**Simultaneous extraction and fractionation of lipids from the microalga
Nannochloropsis sp. for the production of EPA-rich polar lipid concentrates**

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24 **Abstract**

25

26 There is broad scientific evidence on the health benefits of omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty
27 acids (n-3 PUFAs), especially docosahexaenoic acid (DHA, 22:6n3) and eicosapentaenoic
28 acid (EPA, 20:5n3). On the other hand, polar lipids (phospholipids, PLs, and glycolipids,
29 GLs) are excellent emulsifying agents, making them useful both as food products and as
30 excipients for drugs and cosmetics. The bioavailability of n-3 PUFAs in the form of PLs is
31 greater than that of ethyl esters and triacylglycerols. This work has developed an easy method
32 for the simultaneous extraction and fractionation of saponifiable lipids (SLs) from the
33 microalga *Nannochloropsis* sp., using low-toxicity solvents. Firstly, a lipidic fraction very
34 rich in neutral saponifiable lipids (NSLs) was obtained using hexane. Next, an EPA and polar
35 lipids (PLs and GLs)-enriched fraction was obtained using ethanol (96%). Under optimal
36 conditions, in the first extraction with hexane, an SL extract with 86.3% NSLs was obtained;
37 this extract contained 88.9% of the biomass NSLs. Subsequently, in the second extraction step
38 with ethanol (96%), an SL extract with 87.1% polar lipids and up to 35.2% EPA was
39 obtained. This SL extract contained 87.1% of the polar lipids and 74.7% of the EPA from the
40 *Nannochloropsis* sp. biomass.

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42 **KEYWORDS:** extraction, microalga, phospholipid, glycolipid, polar lipid, eicosapentaenoic
43 acid (EPA).

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50 **Introduction**

51

52 There is broad scientific evidence on the health benefits of omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty
53 acids (n-3 PUFAs), especially docosahexaenoic acid (DHA, 22:6n3) and eicosapentaenoic
54 acid (EPA, 20:5n3) (Swanson et al. 2012). These benefits include their ability to reduce
55 cardiovascular problems (Lee et al. 2009), decrease triglyceride levels and increase HDL
56 cholesterol ("good cholesterol") as well as being anti-inflammatory agents (Calder 2012).
57 Whether n-3 PUFAs are used as ingredient in foods, drugs or cosmetics, or as a product in
58 themselves (a nutritional supplement), it is desirable for them to be in the form of
59 concentrates. Therefore, it is convenient to start with raw materials that have a high n-3 PUFA
60 concentration, such as fish oils, krill and microalgae.

61 Polar lipids (phospholipids, PLs, and glycolipids, GLs), on the other hand, are excellent
62 emulsifying agents, making them useful both as food products and as excipients for drugs and
63 cosmetics. PLs are used in pharmaceuticals and cosmetics as emulsifying agents, humectants
64 and liposome constituents (van Hoogevest and Wendel 2014). Several studies also suggest
65 that n-3 PUFAs are more protected against oxidation when they are part of PLs (Burri et al.
66 2012). In addition, the bioavailability of n-3 PUFAs in the form of PLs is greater than that of
67 ethyl esters and triacylglycerols (TAGs) (Tang et al. 2012, Rossmeisl et al. 2012). In this
68 sense, it appears that the n-3 PUFAs in krill oil are better absorbed than those from fish oils
69 because, in the former, a significant portion of the PUFAs are in the form of polar lipids,
70 especially PLs (34-58 % of the total lipids) (Ghasemifard et al. 2014, Burri and Johnsen 2015)
71 and these have emulsifying properties (Mun et al. 2007). Conversely, in a study comparing
72 EPA and DHA absorption from an intake of krill oil and an oil rich in polar lipids from the
73 microalga *Nannochloropsis oculata* (Kagan et al. 2013, 2015), it was observed that
74 microalgal PUFAs were absorbed at a higher rate than the PUFAs from krill oil. Following

75 this, in a similar study using the same oils in rats, Kagan et al. (2015) observed that n-3
76 PUFAs are absorbed better in the form of GLs than as PLs; perhaps because GLs form
77 smaller micelles than those of PLs during digestive hydrolysis. The GLs rich in n-3 PUFAs
78 have been studied less but there are studies where some of these compounds of microalgal
79 origin show antitumor, antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory activity (Da Costa et al. 2016).

80 The best raw materials for obtaining n-3 PUFA concentrates are certain fish oils, krill oil
81 and marine microalgae. Currently, the main source of n-3 PUFA concentrates are fish oils
82 (Finco et al. 2017) but the overexploitation of fishery resources and the growing demand for
83 these oils has led to a search for new, more sustainable and safe sources (Adarme-Vega et al.
84 2014). Krill oil is an alternative source of n-3 PUFAs that is gaining market share. Its
85 production is based on the fishing of the small crustacean *Euphausia superba*, which lives in
86 Antarctic waters (Burri and Johnsen 2015) but its overexploitation might be causing serious
87 damage to polar ecosystems as it is a fundamental link in the food chain (Pottel et al. 2014).
88 Its most notable difference to fish oils is that a large portion of the n-3 PUFAs is found as part
89 of PLs (34-58% of the total lipids) with the rest of its lipid composition being mainly TAGs
90 (23-36%) (Ghasemifard et al. 2014). As a source of n-3 PUFAs, microalgae have the
91 advantages of being cultivatable under controlled conditions, maintaining a constant
92 biochemical composition and eliminating contaminants; they present greater photosynthetic
93 efficiency, biomass productivity and growth rates than most oleaginous crops (Chisti 2007);
94 moreover, microalgal lipids have higher EPA or DHA concentrations than fish oils and higher
95 antioxidant lipid contents (like those of carotenoids). Obtaining n-3 PUFAs from
96 photoautotrophic microalgae, such as *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, *Phaeodactylum tricornerutum*
97 or *Chlorella marina* (species with high EPA contents) will be more sustainable than a culture
98 that is heterotrophic since, in the former, the raw materials are mainly sunlight and CO₂.
99 Marine microalgae cultivated in continuous mode photobioreactors, employing high dilution
100 rates (between 0.2 and 0.3 days⁻¹) present high percentages of polar lipids (structural lipids,

101 primary metabolites associated with growth); these are polar lipids (PLs and GLs) that are
102 particularly rich in n-3 PUFAs (EPA and DHA) (Molina et al. 1999). The microalga
103 *Nannochloropsis* sp. is one of the few species accepted as food and it is of particular interest
104 for the production of high-value oil containing n-3 fatty acids, specifically EPA (Chua and
105 Schenk, 2017).

106 Although great interest exists in obtaining EPA and DHA concentrates from microalgae,
107 there is still no standardized method for the large-scale extraction of lipids; this is due to the
108 great heterogeneity of microalgal lipids (for example, they present different lipid class
109 percentages according to the culture conditions) and the morphological variety, especially in
110 relation to their cell-wall permeability (Servaes et al. 2015). Low-toxicity solvents must be
111 used that are allowed in the manufacture of food products, such as hexane/methanol,
112 hexane/ethanol, hexane/isopropanol and cyclohexane/1-butanol, although these mixtures are
113 better at extracting neutral lipids than polar ones (Ryckebosch et al. 2014a; Servaes et al.
114 2015). The fractionation of the total SLs into these lipidic species has been performed by
115 scaling up the column fractionation method used at the analytical level but the procedure
116 involves huge solvent consumption; this method uses stationary phases based on silica gel and
117 it sequentially elutes neutral lipids (NLs) with chloroform, GLs with acetone and PLs with
118 methanol (Ryckebosch et al. 2012). For the scaled-up methods, stationary phases were used
119 such as silica or modified silica and DEAE-cellulose (diethyl amino ethyl cellulose) while
120 organic solvents of different polarities were used as the mobile phases (Devos et al. 2006,
121 Antonopoulos et al. 2013, Yoshitomi et al. 2011, Christie 2003).

122 To the best of our knowledge, there are no works focused on the specific extraction of
123 polar lipids from microalgae biomass. Some authors, such as Ryckebosh et al. (2014a and
124 2014b) and Servaes et al. (2015) studied the influence of the extraction solvent (hexane,
125 acetone, ethyl acetate, ethanol, etc.) and the extraction method (Shoxlet, pressurized liquids
126 and supercritical extraction) on the extractability of the different lipidic classes (NLs, GLs and

127 PLs). These authors concluded that low polarity solvents are best for the extraction of NLs
128 while the lipids from chloroplasts and membranes, which contain GLs and PLs, respectively,
129 are more effectively extracted using more polar solvents, such as ethanol or methanol.
130 However, direct extraction from the microalgal biomass using polar solvents involves the
131 joint extraction of NLs and polar lipids (Jiménez et al. 2020, Servaes et al. 2015, Ryckebosh
132 et al. 2014 b). Thus, the aim of this work was to obtain EPA-rich polar lipids through the
133 sequential extraction of saponifiable lipids from *Nannochloropsis* sp. biomass using low-
134 toxicity solvents by (i) extraction of NSLs from the original biomass using hexane, and (ii)
135 extraction of EPA-rich polar lipids from the previous residual biomass using ethanol.

136

137 **Materials and Methods**

138

139 *Microalgae and chemicals*

140 The microalga *Nannochloropsis* sp. was purchased in a lyophilized state from Monzón
141 Biotech S.L. (Huesca, Spain). It was chosen for its EPA-rich lipid fraction. The complete lipid
142 composition is described in Section 3.1.

143 The solvents used were ethanol (96% v/v), hexane (95% purity), acetone, methanol
144 and chloroform, all of analytical grade from Panreac AppliChem S.A. (Barcelona, Spain).
145 Nonadecanoic acid (19: 0) was used as the internal standard in the analysis of fatty acids by
146 gas chromatography (GC) (Fluka Analytical, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) and acetyl
147 chloride as the catalyst in the prior methylation (Fluka Analytical). Hydrochloric acid (37%,
148 analytical grade), and magnesium chloride 6-hydrate (both from Panreac AppliChem S.A.)
149 were used for the determination of total lipids. Finally, silica-gel cartridges (Sep-pack plus
150 WAT020520, Waters Corporation, Milford, MA) were used for the SL fractionation.

151

152 *Sequential lipid extraction from microalgal biomass*

153 To produce EPA-rich polar lipid concentrates, a step-by-step extraction was
154 developed. Firstly, hexane was used to try to specifically remove the neutral lipids from the
155 original biomass. Next, ethanol (96% v/v) was used to extract an EPA and polar lipid-
156 enriched fraction from the residual biomass. Figure 1 shows the laboratory-scale lipid
157 extraction procedure. The first extraction step was carried out treating 2.5 g of dry biomass
158 with different amounts of hexane - the solvent/biomass ratios tested were 5, 10, 20 and 30 mL
159 hexane/g dry biomass (db). Extractions were carried out at 20, 40 or 60 °C in bottles with
160 screw caps, placed on a water submersible magnetic stirrer (Variomag maxi, Thermo Fisher
161 Scientific, Germany). The extraction mixture was agitated at 300 rpm for time periods
162 between 1 and 20 h. After the extraction, the mixture obtained was filtered (Pobel glass plate,
163 porosity 4, Madrid, Spain) and the hexanic extract collected and fitted to a known volume
164 (100 mL). Residual biomass was then recovered and used in the second extraction step with
165 ethanol (96%). Different amounts of ethanol (5-30 mL/g original db) and temperatures (20-60
166 °C) were also tested in bottles with screw caps, placed on a water submersible magnetic plate
167 agitated at 300 rpm for 20 h. Finally, the mixture obtained was filtered (Pobel glass plate,
168 porosity 4, Madrid, Spain) and the ethanolic extract collected and fitted to a known volume
169 (100 mL). Both hexanic and ethanolic extracts were characterized by determining the
170 parameters described in Section 2.3.

171 The scaling up of the extraction process was carried out in 2 L glass reactors, equipped
172 with 4 baffles, jacketed for temperature control and agitated at 400 rpm with a propeller stirrer
173 (Eurostar digital, IKA, Staufen, Germany). In these experiments, 50 g of lyophilized biomass
174 from *Nannochloropsis sp.* were extracted using 0.5 L of hexane and ethanol (96%) in the first
175 and second extraction step, respectively.

176 The maximal SL yield in the extraction with hexane was measured by Soxhlet
177 extraction. To do this, 2.5 g of dry biomass was weighed into a cellulose cartridge and placed

178 in a Soxhlet device. Microalgal lipids were extracted for 8 h using 300 mL of hexane (12
179 reflows per hour).

180 To compare the previous extractions carried out on the dry biomass, the extraction-
181 fractionation procedure was also applied to wet biomass. In this case, certain tests were
182 carried out using wet biomass with an 86 wt% water content (2.5 g of lyophilized biomass
183 was resuspended in 15.35 mL of water). The extraction steps were carried out at 40 °C for 20
184 h using 10 mL of solvent/g equivalent of dry biomass.

185

186 *Analytical methods*

187 *Determination of the total lipid (TLs), saponifiable lipid (SLs) and fatty acid composition*

188 Total lipids (TLs) include both saponifiable lipids (SLs, lipids containing fatty acids) and non-
189 saponifiable lipids. SLs comprise neutral saponifiable lipids (NSLs, such as acylglycerols and
190 free fatty acids) and polar lipids (such as glycolipids and phospholipids, GLs and PLs). The
191 TL content of microalgal biomass was determined using the method described by Kochet
192 (1978), which is based on the extraction of lipids from lyophilized biomass with
193 chloroform/methanol (1:1 v/v).

194 To determine the SL content of the biomass samples, lyophilized algal biomass (three
195 10 mg samples of each algal batch) was directly transesterified in 1 mL of hexane and 0.125
196 mg of internal standard (nonadecaenoic acid, 19:0), using 1 mL of a 1:20 v/v solution of
197 acetyl chloride in methanol. The reactions were conducted in tubes heated to 105 °C for 20
198 min for transmethylation. Next, the mixture was cooled to room temperature and 1 mL of
199 water was added. The tubes were then agitated and centrifuged. Two phases were formed, the
200 upper one (hexane) containing the FAMEs obtained from the SLs present in the microalgal
201 biomass. These FAMEs were analysed by gas chromatography (GC). This analysis was
202 carried out in an Agilent Technologies 6890N chromatograph (Santa Clara, USA), equipped
203 with a capillary column of fused silica OmegaWax™ (0.25 mm × 30 m, 0.25 µm standard

204 film, Supelco, Bellefonte, PA) and a flame ionization detector (FID). Nitrogen was the carrier
205 gas at a flow rate of 58.1 mL/min and a split ratio of 1:40. The injector and detector
206 temperatures were set at 250 and 260 °C, respectively. The oven temperature was initially set
207 at 150 °C for 3 min, then programmed to increase to 240 °C at a rate of 7.5 °C/min and set at
208 240 °C for 12 min. This analysis gave the SL content per unit mass of dry biomass and the
209 fatty acid composition of microalgal SLs. The fatty acid composition of the SLs was
210 determined by comparing the retention times to those of the PUFA-3 Menhaden oil standard
211 (Supelco, Bellefonte, PA, USA) analyzed under the same conditions (Jiménez et al., 2014).

212 In addition, the amounts of extracted SLs and their fatty acid profiles in each
213 extraction step were determined by methylation and GC analysis of the samples. In the case of
214 the hexanic extracts, 0.5 mL of lipid extract was taken and mixed with another 0.5 mL of
215 hexane before sample methylation. With ethanolic extracts, 0.5 mL of sample were firstly
216 dried under a nitrogen stream and then mixed with 1 mL of hexane.

217 The SL yield (wt%), both in hexanic and ethanolic extracts, is defined as the
218 percentage of extracted SLs with respect to the total amount of the SLs contained in the
219 original biomass (Eq. 1). Similarly, the NSL, GL and PL yields (wt%) is defined as the
220 percentage of each of the lipid types recovered with respect to the total content of that lipid
221 type in the original biomass (Eq. 2).

222

$$223 \text{ SL yield (wt\%)} = \frac{(100 \times \text{SLs recovered})}{\text{SLs contained in the original biomass}} \quad (1)$$

224

$$225 \text{ NSL, GL or PL yield (wt\%)} = \frac{(100 \times \text{NSLs, GLs or PLs recovered})}{\text{NSLs, GLs or PLs contained in the original biomass}} \quad (2)$$

226

227 Similarly, the EPA yield (wt%), both in the hexanic and ethanolic extract, is defined as the
228 percentage of extracted EPA with respect to the total amount of EPA contained in the original
229 biomass (Eq. 3).

230

$$231 \quad \text{EPA yield (wt\%)} = \frac{(100 \times \text{EPA recovered in the extract})}{\text{EPA contained in the original biomass}} \quad (3)$$

232

233 *Determination of neutral saponifiable lipids (NSLs), glycolipids (GLs) and phospholipids*
234 *(PLs)*

235 The TLs extracted from the microalgal biomass and some of the hexane and ethanol lipidic
236 extracts were separated into neutral saponifiable lipids (NSLs), glycolipids (GLs) and
237 phospholipids (PLs) following the Kates (1986) procedure. This fractionation was carried out
238 by eluting the microalgal lipids in silica-gel cartridges. Samples with around 10 mg of SLs
239 were evaporated under a nitrogen stream and resuspended in 0.5 mL of chloroform. The
240 samples were loaded into the cartridge and eluted with 30 mL of chloroform to collect the
241 NSL fraction. Then, 30 mL of acetone were used along with 20 mL of chloroform:methanol
242 (85:15 v/v) to collect the GLs; and finally, 30 mL of methanol was used to elute the PL
243 fraction. The GC analysis of all fractions gave the percentage of each lipid class with respect
244 to the total SLs and their fatty acid profile (Jiménez et al. 2014).

245

246 *Statistical analysis*

247 All the experiments and analyses were carried out at least twice and the results were
248 expressed as the arithmetic mean \pm the standard deviation. The results were evaluated in terms
249 of ANOVA using Statgraphics 18 Software. P-values below 0.05 were considered statistically
250 significant.

251

252 **Results and discussion**

253

254 *Lipidic composition of the microalgal biomass*

255 The *Nannochloropsis sp.* microalgal biomass used contained 15.0 ± 0.4 wt% of SLs and 25.7
256 ± 0.7 wt% of TLs (both with respect to the biomass dry weight). Figure 2A shows the fatty
257 acid composition of the SLs from the *Nannochloropsis sp.*: EPA (20:5n3) accounted for 22.1
258 ± 0.0 wt% of the total fatty acids. Polar lipids were much richer in the EPA (49.4 ± 0.4 wt%
259 GLs and $18.3\% \pm 0.2$ wt% PLs of the total fatty acids in each lipid class) than the NSLs ($6.3 \pm$
260 0.3 wt%) (Fig. 2A). On the other hand, the fractionation of TLs extracted from the biomass
261 resulted in 53.0 ± 0.9 wt% of SLs being NSLs, 32.8 ± 1.7 wt% being GLs and 14.2 ± 0.7 wt%
262 being PLs (Fig. 3A, original biomass). This means that 85% of the total EPA is contained in
263 the polar lipids (73.3% in GLs and 11.8% in PLs, Fig. 2B). This is common in
264 photoautotrophic algae because the PUFAs in them are mainly accumulated in complex polar
265 lipids constituting the membranes (López et al. 1998; Guihéneuf et al. 2015). This means that
266 the polar lipid concentration or the fractionation of SLs into NSLs and polar lipids occurs
267 alongside a certain EPA concentration in the polar-lipid fraction.

268

269 *Previous results regarding microalgal lipid extraction*

270 In our work, the lipid extraction was carried out using low-toxicity solvents, such as hexane
271 and ethanol (96%), which are allowed in the manufacture of food products. Table 1 shows the
272 results of the SL extraction from *N. gaditana* microalgal biomass carried out in a previous
273 work (Jiménez et al. 2014). This table shows that, using hexane, SLs were extracted with a
274 yield of 56.7%, a value a little smaller than the percentage of NSLs in the biomass (65.4%).
275 The fractionation of extracted SLs showed that 88.2% of these were NSLs and only 11.8%
276 were polar lipids (GLs in this case; PLs were not detected in this extract). These results were
277 obtained from a *N. gaditana* batch that contained 24.1% TLs and 12.0% SLs (both in biomass
278 dry weight), similar to the contents of the biomass used in this work. Predictably, if hexane (a
279 non-polar solvent, $\log P = 4$, Sangster 1989) is used in the first extraction step, it is mainly
280 NSLs that are extracted; thus, we can next extract the polar lipids from the residual biomass

281 using a more polar solvent such as ethanol (log P = -0.30). In this way, we can separate NSLs
282 and polar lipids. In fact, in recent research work on SL extraction from *N. gaditana* biomass
283 with ethanol (96%) (Jiménez et al. 2020), the GL and PL yields obtained were over 99%
284 when extraction was carried out from lyophilized *N. gaditana* biomass at 20 °C for 24 h;
285 however, in this case these polar lipids were extracted together with NSLs.

286

287 *Simultaneous extraction and fractionation of microalgal lipids from Nannochloropsis sp.*
288 *lyophilized biomass*

289 Taking these previous results into account, we planned experiments carrying out a first
290 extraction with hexane and then a second extraction from the residual biomass using ethanol
291 (96%). In the first hexane extraction step, we primarily expected to extract NSLs with a low
292 EPA content (around 6.3% of total fatty acids, Fig 2A) while in the second extraction step
293 with ethanol, we expected to extract mainly EPA-rich polar lipids, thus fractionating the total
294 SLs of the microalgal biomass. In any case, this extraction-fractionation would not be easy
295 because in microalgal cells, the two lipidic species are not completely isolated. Many neutral
296 lipids interact through weak van der Waals forces to form lipid globules in the cytoplasm;
297 these relatively free neutral lipids can be extracted from the cells using non-polar solvents
298 such as hexane, since similar van der Waals forces are formed between the neutral lipids and
299 the non-polar solvent. However, some neutral lipids form complexes with polar lipids, which
300 also form hydrogen bonds with proteins in the cell membrane; non-polar solvents are not
301 capable of disrupting these hydrogen bonds so they cannot extract these complexed neutral
302 lipids and the polar lipids from the cell. In contrast, polar organic solvents can form hydrogen
303 bonds with the lipids from these complexes and hence break the lipid-protein complexes,
304 leading to extraction of the complexed neutral lipids and the polar lipids from the cells (Halim
305 et al. 2012; Shahidi and Wanasundara 2002; Ryckeboosh et al. 2014).

306 The two-step extraction was initially applied to lyophilized *Nannochloropsis* sp.
307 biomass. Table 2 shows the results of the two-step hexane-ethanol (96%) extraction. Table 2A
308 shows that the SL yield obtained in the first extraction with hexane (49.4%) was, as expected,
309 quite similar to the NSL content of this biomass (53.0%). However, the hexanic fraction
310 contained 12.9% EPA, a high percentage considering that the NSLs of the biomass contain
311 6.3% EPA (Fig. 2A). The fractionation of this hexane extract into NSLs and polar lipids (GLs
312 and PLs) (Table 2B) demonstrated that, as expected, it was very rich in NSLs (73.6%);
313 however, it also contained an appreciable amount of polar lipids (26.4%), which explains the
314 high EPA content. The NSLs in this extract contained 6.3% EPA, exactly the same percentage
315 as that for the NSLs in the biomass. So, by using hexane, not only were the 68.6% of NSLs
316 contained in the biomass recovered but also the 27.7% of polar lipids (Table 2B), an
317 excessive amount when considering the objective of this work. Similar results were obtained
318 by Ryckeboosh et al. (2014a) from different microalgal species (*Isochrysis galbana*,
319 *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, *Nannochloropsis* sp. and *Phaedactylum tricormutum*) testing
320 several extraction solvent systems. For all the microalgae tested, the neutral lipid (NL)
321 content in the hexane extract was higher than the content in the original biomass; for example,
322 the hexane extract from *Nannochloropsis* sp. biomass contained around 80% of NLs, higher
323 than the NL content of the biomass (46.5%). In this case, only 35% of the NLs contained in
324 the biomass were recovered in the hexane extract. Also, similar to our results, polar lipids
325 (GLs and PLs) were found in this hexane extract (19.8% of polar lipids in the biomass).

326 In the second extraction with ethanol, the SL yield (37.3%, Table 2A) was small
327 considering that the biomass contained 47.0% polar lipids; this result agrees with the
328 relatively high percentage of polar lipids extracted with hexane (27.7%) and the 13.3% of SLs
329 still contained in the residual biomass after this second extraction step (Table 2A, Fig. 1).
330 Consequently, new conditions should be tested to increase this last SL yield. The ethanolic
331 extract contained 31.3% EPA (Table 2A), which is lower than the average EPA content in the

332 polar lipids (40.0%; calculated from the EPA content of GLs, 49.4%, and PLs, 18.3%, Fig.
333 2A). This ethanolic extract contained 72.5% polar lipids and 27.4% NSLs (Table 2B), which
334 means that 57.6% of the total polar lipids were recovered in this extract. It is difficult to
335 compare these results with the ones obtained by other authors because few works were found
336 that carried out a sequential lipid extraction from the microalgal biomass with the goal of
337 clearly separating NLs and polar lipids. Castejón and Señoráns (2019) carried out a three-step
338 consecutive extraction on *Nannochloropsis gaditana* biomass using pressurized solvents with
339 the aim of obtaining fractions of decreasing polarity: a first extraction with water at 60°C to
340 eliminate polar compounds, such as carbohydrates or peptides, a second extraction with
341 ethanol at 90°C to extract polar lipids and a third with hexane at 120°C to extract the non-
342 polar lipids. However, after the ethanol extraction (step 2), the biomass was exhausted (a
343 12.6% extraction yield of biomass dry weight) and in the following hexane extraction step, a
344 low lipid yield was obtained (1.3%). This result is consistent with data from the literature
345 since ethanol can extract both NLs and polar lipids from *Nannochloropsis gaditana* biomass
346 at high yields of up to 99% (Jiménez et al., 2020).

347 Using this procedure, we obtained an hexanic extract appreciably richer in NSLs
348 (73.6%) than SLs from the biomass (53.0%), and an ethanolic extract with 72.5% polar lipids
349 (appreciably higher than the biomass polar lipid content, 47.0%); furthermore, this ethanolic
350 extract contained 31.3% EPA (appreciably higher than the 22.1% of EPA in the biomass).
351 The polar lipids and EPA recovery yields in the ethanolic extract were, respectively, 57.6%
352 (of the polar lipids contained in the biomass) and 52.8% (of the EPA contained in the
353 biomass; or 62.1% of the EPA contained in the biomass polar lipids). These results support
354 the objective of this work because we were able to obtain a polar lipid and EPA-enriched
355 ethanolic extract.

356

357 *Optimization of the hexane-ethanol extraction steps from the lyophilized biomass*

358 To improve the previous results, a study on the extraction conditions for both steps
359 was carried out. Table 3 and Figure 3 show the results of the experiments to optimize both the
360 hexane and ethanol extraction steps, with the aim of finding more appropriate values for the
361 temperature, time and solvent/biomass ratio, required for attaining high NSL and polar lipid
362 yields when extracting with hexane and ethanol, respectively.

363 Table 3A shows that, in the SL extraction with hexane, increasing the extraction
364 temperature from 20 to 40 and 60°C (Experiments 1 to 3) increased the SL yield to a
365 maximum value of 54.6% at 40°C (for 20 h and 30 mL hexane/g biomass). Hence, this
366 temperature was chosen to study the influence of the hexane/biomass ratio. Experiment 2 and
367 Experiments 4 to 6 show that a SL yield of 54.0% was achieved using only 10 mL hexane/g
368 biomass (no significant differences were obtained between the SL yields achieved with 10, 20
369 and 30 mL/g). When this ratio was reduced to 5 mL/g biomass, the SL yield decreased to
370 45.3%. In an attempt to reduce the extraction time as well, extraction was carried out at 40°C,
371 10 mL/g for 8 h (Experiment 7); however, under these conditions, the SL yield likewise
372 decreased to 44.0%. Then, to carry out extractions using short reaction times, three
373 experiments were carried out at 60°C, 10 mL/g for times of 1, 4 and 8 h (Experiments 8 to
374 10). These experiments show that at 60°C, 8 h and 10 mL/g, an SL yield of 55.6% was
375 obtained, similar to that achieved at 40°C, 20 h and 10 mL/g (54.0%). Therefore, similar SL
376 yields can be achieved under different condition combinations. It seems clear that the optimal
377 conditions, producing similarly high SL yields (around 54.0-55.6%), will be obtained from
378 economically balancing the considerations of energy consumption (related to temperature and
379 time) and solvent consumption.

380 An extraction experiment using 40°C, 20 h and 10 mL/g (Experiment 11) was
381 performed using 50 g of lyophilized biomass instead of the 2.5 g used in all previous
382 experiments (a scaling-up factor of 20). Similar SL yields were obtained under the same
383 conditions for both scales (54.0%, Exp. 5 and 52.9%, Exp. 11). These maximum SL yields

384 were similar to the NSL content of the biomass (53.0%) and close to the SL yield achieved by
385 Soxhlet extraction (57.9%, Experiment 12, Table 3), which would indicate that good
386 extraction of this lipid type could have been achieved using hexane. However, these extracts
387 contained 9.1-14.9% EPA, duplicating the EPA content of the NSLs (6.3%, Fig. 2A).

388 To gain insight into the lipid class composition of the extracted fractions, two of these
389 extracts were fractionated into NSLs, GLs and PLs (Fig. 3). The hexanic extract obtained at
390 40°C, 20 h and 30 mL/g (Exp. 2, 54.6% SL yield) contained 86.3% NSLs and only 13.7%
391 polar lipids (Fig. 3A); 88.9% of the NSLs contained in the original biomass were extracted
392 (Fig. 3B) and these NSLs contained 6.3% EPA (the same value as the NSLs in the original
393 biomass); however, 21.1% of the GLs and 3.8% of the PLs contained in the biomass were
394 also extracted (Fig. 3B), which means that 32.4% of the biomass EPA was extracted (Fig. 3B,
395 EPA content of this extract was 13.1%, Table 3A). In addition, we fractionated the hexane
396 extract from the extraction carried out at 40°C, 20 h and only 5 mL/g, which resulted in a
397 lower SL yield of 45.3% (Exp. 6). In this case, the hexanic extract contained 93.7% NSLs
398 (Fig. 3A), although a lower percentage of the NSLs contained in the biomass were extracted
399 (80.0%, Fig. 3B). Comparing the results of Experiments 6 and 2 indicates that the higher the
400 SL extraction yield (45.3 and 54.6, respectively, Table 3A), the higher the NSL yield (80.0
401 and 88.9%, respectively, Fig. 3B) but also the more polar lipids were extracted (especially
402 GLs, with polar lipid yields of 24.9% and 9.6% in Experiments 6 and 2, respectively, Fig.
403 3B), which decreased the NSL percentage in the hexanic extract (93.7% and 86.3%,
404 respectively). Therefore, if high NSL yields are preferred, we should choose conditions under
405 which the SL extraction yield is high (Experiment 2, with a high hexane/biomass ratio).
406 Conversely, if we prefer to obtain an extract rich in NSLs (Fig. 2A), we should choose
407 conditions under which the SL extraction yields are moderate (Experiment 6, with a lower
408 hexane/biomass ratio). In any case, under the conditions specified, very rich NSL hexanic
409 extracts were obtained (86.3-93.7% NSLs) with high recoveries of these lipids (above 80%).

410 Subsequently, five of the residual biomasses from the hexanic extractions
411 (Experiments 2, 3, 5, 6 and 11, Table 3A) were subjected to a second extraction step with
412 ethanol (96%) (Table 3B). Each of these five ethanol extractions was performed under the
413 same conditions of temperature, time and solvent/dry biomass ratio as the first hexane
414 extraction step (Table 3A). Table 3B shows that, for Experiments 2 and 3 (carried out by
415 modifying the temperature), similar SL yields were achieved; so, under these conditions (20 h
416 and 30 mL/g), the lower 40°C temperature was preferable (Experiment 2). Experiments 2, 5
417 and 6 (carried out by modifying only the ethanol/biomass ratio) show that small decreases in
418 the SL yields were observed when reducing the ethanol (96%)/biomass residue ratio from 30
419 to 10 and 5 mL/g. Hence, the middle ethanol (96%)/biomass ratio of 10 mL/g was chosen for
420 scaling up. In Experiment 11, the residual biomass from extracting 50 g of biomass with
421 hexane (a scaling-up factor of 20) was extracted under the same conditions as in Experiment 5
422 (40°C, 20 h and 10 mL/g), obtaining a SL yield of 42.9% (similar to that obtained at the small
423 scale, 43.3%). Thus, in this larger-scale experiment, a total SL yield of 95.8% was achieved
424 (52.9% with hexane, Table 3A, and 42.9% with ethanol, Table 3B). The SL yields shown in
425 Table 3B are similar to, or a little lower than, the polar lipid content of the biomass (32.8% of
426 GLs and 14.2% of PLs, Fig 3A), which would indicate that the ethanol mainly extracted the
427 polar lipids, as previously the hexane had mainly extracted NSLs. The EPA content of these
428 SLs (33.4-35.2%, Table 3B) was a little lower than the EPA content of the polar lipids (40%,
429 Fig 2A).

430 Three of these ethanolic extracts were fractionated into NSLs, GLs and PLs (Figs. 3
431 and 4). The extract obtained in Experiment 2 (an SL yield of 46.8%, Table 3B) contained only
432 12.7% NSLs and 87.3% polar lipids (56.4% of which were GLs and 30.9% PLs, Fig. 3A) with
433 nearly 81% of the GLs and the totality of PLs contained in the biomass being extracted (Fig.
434 3B); and these GLs and PLs contained 42.7% and 20.0% EPA, respectively (contents that
435 were very close to the GLs and PLs in the original biomass at 49.4% and 18.3%, respectively;

436 Fig. 2A). We also fractionated the ethanolic extract from the extraction carried out at 40°C, 20
437 h and only 5 mL/g (Experiment 6, Table 3B), which produced a slightly lower SL yield
438 (42.4%, Table 3B). In this case, the extract contained 82% polar lipids (55.2% GLs and
439 26.8% PLs, Fig. 3A); 71% of the GLs and 80% of the PLs present in the biomass being
440 extracted (Fig. 3B) - these lower polar lipid yields were possibly due to the lower
441 ethanol/biomass ratio used. Comparing the results of Experiments 2 and 6, we see that, to
442 obtain an ethanolic extract with the highest polar lipid content (87.3%, Experiment 2, Fig.
443 3A), the NSLs should be extracted with a high yield in the first hexane extraction step, even if
444 this involves a loss in terms of polar lipids. The ethanolic extract from Experiment 6 contains
445 less polar lipids (82%, Fig. 3A); this is also probably due to the higher NSL content of the
446 biomass residue from which the extraction was performed, since the SL yield (and therefore
447 the NSL yield) in the hexane extraction was lower than in Experiment 2.

448 Additionally, we fractionated the hexanic and ethanolic extracts from Experiment 11
449 (Table 3A and B). The ethanolic extract was obtained from the biomass residue following the
450 hexane extraction carried out on 50 g of biomass (Experiment 11, Table 3A). The NSL, GL
451 and PL composition of this ethanolic SL extract is shown in Fig. 4A, the composition of
452 which was similar to that in Experiment 2 (the differences between the NSL, GL and PL
453 compositions of both ethanolic extracts not being significant, Figs. 3A and 4A); nonetheless,
454 lower polar lipid recoveries were obtained (76.5% GLs and 88.2% PLs, Fig. 4B), which was
455 due to the lower ethanol/biomass ratio used in this case (10 mL ethanol/g and 30 mL/g used in
456 Experiment 2). In this scaled-up experiment, the SL fraction contained 87.7% polar lipids (Fig
457 4A) and 35.2% EPA (Table 3B) while 80% of the polar lipids contained in the biomass were
458 recovered (Fig. 4B).

459 Figures 3 and 4 therefore show how effectively we obtained hexanic extracts using
460 this procedure, with an NSL content up to 86.3-93.7%, and where 88.9-80.0% of the NSLs
461 contained in the biomass were recovered; these NSL contents are considerable higher than the

462 NSL content of the biomass (53.0%) and much higher than that achieved in the first
463 fractionation experiment (73.6% NSLs, Table 2). These figures also show that an ethanolic
464 fraction with up to 87.3-87.7% polar lipids (56.4% GLs, 30.9% PLs) and around 35.2% EPA
465 (Table 3B) was obtained, considerably higher than the polar lipid and EPA content of the
466 biomass (47% and 22.1%, respectively) and that achieved in the first fractionation experiment
467 (72.5% and 31.3%, respectively, Table 2). In terms of EPA, 65.0-74.7% of that contained in
468 the biomass was recovered in the ethanolic fractions. Thus, the proposed methodology
469 (summarized in Fig. 1) allows us to obtain EPA-rich polar lipid concentrates from the
470 simultaneous extraction and fractionation of the SLs present in the *Nannochloropsis* sp.
471 microalga using an extraction solvent which is permitted in the food industry. For this, it is
472 essential to achieve SL yields close to the NSL content of the original biomass in the first
473 hexane extraction step so that the biomass is practically exhausted of NSLs. The subsequent
474 extraction with ethanol from the residual biomass ensures an extract which not only contains
475 high polar lipid yields from the biomass, but also an EPA-enriched extract (since this fatty
476 acid is mainly located in the polar lipids).

477

478 *Extraction-fractionation of SLs from wet Nannochloropsis sp. biomass*

479 Generally, microalgal biomass lyophilization is considered to be an expensive
480 operation because it requires costly equipment and consumes an appreciable amount of
481 energy. From wet biomass, higher solvent/biomass ratios are usually required to achieve
482 similar SL yields. In this respect, Malekzadeh et al. (2016) demonstrated that the SL
483 extraction yield from *Chlorella vulgaris* using different hexane-methanol mixtures (from 1:0
484 to 0:1 v:v) was lower, the higher the biomass water content (these authors tested lyophilized
485 and wet biomasses with 70% and 80% water contents); the reduction in yield being more
486 intense when hexane was the dominant portion of the solvent mixture. Moreover, the ethanol

487 recovery costs were greater using wet biomass since the ethanol have to be separated from a
488 great amount of water (Jiménez et al. 2020).

489 In any case, to compare the previous results obtained using lyophilized biomass, the
490 two step hexane-ethanol (96%) extraction procedure was applied to wet biomass with a water
491 content of 86 wt%, which is a typical water content after the biomass harvested from the
492 photobioreactor is centrifuged. The two extraction steps were carried out at 40°C for 20 h
493 using 10 mL of solvent/g of equivalent dry biomass (the same conditions as in Experiments 5
494 and 11, Table 3). In this experiment, the hexane and ethanol SL extraction yields were 51.0%
495 and 39.8%, respectively; a little lower than the yields obtained from dry biomass under the
496 same conditions (54.0% and 43.3%, respectively, Table 3), which is logical given the
497 presence of water. The EPA content of the hexane and ethanolic extracts were 18.0 and 26.5%
498 higher and lower, respectively, than the EPA contents of the extracts obtained from
499 lyophilized biomass (13.5% and 35.2%, respectively, Table 3). Figure 4 compares the results
500 of this extraction-fractionation experiment (Hexanic Exp. Wet, Ethanolic Exp. Wet) with that
501 previously obtained from the lyophilized biomass (Hexanic Exp. 11, Ethanolic Exp. 11). This
502 figure shows that the separation of both lipidic species was worse than when using lyophilized
503 biomass even though the NSLs and polar lipids were mostly extracted in the hexane and
504 ethanol extract, respectively. In this case, the SL extracted with hexane contained 63.6% NSL
505 (Fig. 4A), and only 61.2% of the NSLs contained in the biomass were extracted (Fig. 4B).
506 The ethanol fraction contained 60.5% polar lipids (Fig. 4A, Ethanolic Exp. Wet), and only
507 53.1% of the GLs and 47.7% of the PLs contained in the biomass were extracted with ethanol;
508 both percentages being considerably lower than the 76.5% and 88.2% achieved, respectively,
509 from the lyophilized biomass (Ethanolic exp. 11, Fig. 4B). Perhaps the presence of water
510 decreased the selectivity of hexane and ethanol towards neutral and polar lipids, respectively.
511 On the other hand, other reasons might influence this poorer separation of both lipid species.
512 Firstly, the SL extraction yields were lower than those achieved from lyophilized biomass due

513 to the presence of water. In this regard, with the wet biomass, we used the extraction
514 conditions optimized for lyophilized biomass whereas the wet biomass might require different
515 extraction conditions; for example, higher solvent/biomass ratios. Consequently, further
516 experiments need to be carried out with wet biomass, similar to those shown in Table 3, if we
517 wish to improve the separation of NSLs and polar lipids.

518

519 **Conclusions**

520

521 A procedure was developed to extract SL fractions rich in NSLs and EPA-enriched polar
522 lipids (GLs and PLs) from *Nannochloropsis* sp. lyophilized biomass. Under the optimal
523 conditions in a first hexane extraction step, an SL extract with 86.3-93.7% NSLs was
524 obtained; this extract contained 88.9-80.0% of the NSLs present in the biomass.

525 Subsequently, in a second extraction step with ethanol (96%), an SL extract was obtained
526 with 82.0-87.7% polar lipids and up to 35.2% EPA. This SL extract contained up to 87.1% of
527 the polar lipids and 74.7% of the EPA present in the *Nannochloropsis* sp. biomass.

528

529 **Author contributions**

530 All authors have contributed to the manuscript. All authors contributed to the research design,
531 data analyses, and all of them revised, edited and approved the final manuscript. The
532 experimental work was carried out by María José Jiménez Callejón.

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Table 1. Previous results regarding microalgal lipid extraction using hexane: (A) Composition in lipidic classes and EPA content of SLs, NSLs, GLs and PLs of *Nannochloropsis gaditana* microalgal biomass (Jiménez *et al.*, 2014). (B) Extraction of SLs¹: SL yield, composition in lipidic classes and EPA content of the extracted lipidic classes.

(A)	SLs	NSLs	GLs	PLs
Lipidic species (wt%)	100	65.4 ± 1.1	31.2 ± 1.1	3.4 ± 0.0
EPA content (wt%) ²	24.8 ± 0.3	20.6 ± 0.0	33.8 ± 0.1	23.7 ± 0.0
(B)				
SL yield (wt%) ³	56.7 ± 0.0			
Lipidic classes (wt%)		88.2 ± 0.1	11.8 ± 0.1	0.0 ± 0.0
EPA content (wt%) ²	15.8 ± 0.0	14.8 ± 0.2	23.7 ± 0.3	

¹ *Operational conditions:* 35.7 g of wet biomass (86% water; 24.1% of TLs and 12.0% of SLs of biomass dry weight) homogenized at 1700 bars, 10 mL hexane/g dry biomass, 22°C, 20 h.
² of total fatty acid; ³ Equation (1).

655

656

Table 2. Simultaneous extraction and fractionation of microalgal lipids from *Nannochloropsis sp.* lyophilized biomass by sequential extraction hexane – ethanol (96% v/v): (A) SL yields and EPA content in the hexanic and ethanolic extracts and in the residual biomass II (not extracted lipids) (B) Composition in lipidic classes, recovery of NSLs and polar lipids and EPA content of each lipidic class of both extracts.

	Hexanic Extract	Ethanolic Extract	Residual Biomass II
(A)			
SL yield (wt%) ¹	49.4 ± 0.2	37.3 ± 1.2	13.3 ± 0.1
EPA content (wt%) ²	12.9 ± 0.0	31.3 ± 0.7	33.6 ± 0.4
(B)			
Composition in lipidic classes (wt%)			
NSLs	73.6 ± 0.3	27.4 ± 1.1	
GLs	12.7 ± 0.7	41.8 ± 1.5	
PLs	13.7 ± 0.3	30.7 ± 0.4	
Lipid yield (wt%) ³			
NSLs	68.6 ± 0.3	19.3 ± 0.8	
Polar lipids	27.7 ± 0.3	57.6 ± 0.9	
EPA content (wt%) ²			
NSLs	6.3 ± 0.1	9.4 ± 3.1	
GLs	46.7 ± 2.4	48.7 ± 0.3	
PLs	12.9 ± 0.6	16.9 ± 0.0	

Operational conditions: 2.5 g of lyophilized biomass (15.0 ± 0.4 w% of SLs, 22.1 ± 0.0 wt% of the EPA in the total fatty acids, Section 3.1). Hexane extraction: 75 mL hexane, 20 h, 20 °C, 300 rpm. Ethanol extraction: 75 mL ethanol (96%), 20 h, 20 °C, 300 rpm.

¹ Equation (1); ² of total fatty acid; ³ Equation (2)

657

Table 3. SL extraction from (A) lyophilized *Nannochloropsis sp.* biomass using hexane and (B) residual biomass of *Nannochloropsis sp.* previously extracted with hexane, using ethanol, under different conditions: the influence of temperature, time and solvent/biomass ratio on the SL yield and EPA content.

(A)					
Hexane/biomass					
Exp.	T (°C)	T (h)	ratio (mL/g)	SL yield (wt%) ¹	EPA content (wt%) ²
1	20	20	30	49.4 ± 0.2 ^a	12.9 ± 0.0
2	40	20	30	54.6 ± 2.2 ^{b,c}	13.1 ± 2.1
3	60	20	30	54.3 ± 0.5 ^{b,c}	13.1 ± 0.2
4	40	20	20	53.9 ± 0.4 ^{b,c}	13.8 ± 0.2
5	40	20	10	54.0 ± 0.4 ^{b,c}	13.6 ± 0.1
6	40	20	5	45.3 ± 0.9 ^d	8.9 ± 0.2
7	40	8	10	44.0 ± 1.4 ^d	8.8 ± 0.1
8	60	8	10	55.6 ± 1.0 ^c	14.9 ± 0.1
9	60	4	10	49.1 ± 0.7 ^a	11.9 ± 0.3
10	60	1	10	44.5 ± 0.1 ^d	9.1 ± 0.2
11*	40	20	10	52.9 ± 0.5 ^b	13.5 ± 0.1
12	Soxhlet	8	Soxhlet	57.9 ± 3.9 ^e	17.5 ± 0.3
(B)					
Ethanol/biomass					
Exp.	T (°C)	T (h)	ratio (mL/g)	SL yield (%) ¹	EPA content (wt%) ²
2	40	20	30	46.8 ± 0.1 ^{a'}	35.2 ± 0.3
3	60	20	30	46.1 ± 0.8 ^{a'}	33.4 ± 0.6
5	40	20	10	43.3 ± 0.3 ^{b'}	35.0 ± 0.2
6	40	20	5	42.4 ± 1.1 ^{b'}	33.9 ± 0.1
11	40	20	10	42.9 ± 0.1 ^{b'}	35.2 ± 0.1

659 *Operational conditions:* (A) 2.5 g of lyophilized biomass (Section 3.1), 300 rpm. * 50 g of
 660 biomass. (B) Residual biomass from the hexanic extractions, 300 rpm.¹ Equation (1); ² of total
 661 fatty acid. ^{a, b, c, d, e} show no significant differences in SL yield between the hexanic extracts
 662 with the same letter ($\alpha = 0.05$). ^{a', b'} show no significant differences in SL yield between the
 663 ethanolic extracts with the same letter ($\alpha = 0.05$). Data are shown as mean ± SD, n = 2.

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671 *Figure 1.* Scheme of the simultaneous extraction and fractionation of microalgal lipids from

672 *Nannochloropsis* sp. lyophilized biomass in two steps using hexane and ethanol (96% v/v).

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679 *Figure 2.* Lipid composition of *Nannochloropsis sp.* microalgal biomass: (A) Fatty acid
 680 composition (weight percentage of total fatty acids) of total saponifiable lipids (▨ SLs) and of
 681 each of the lipidic classes (■ NSLs, ▣ GLs and □ PLs) obtained by fractionation of TLs; (B)
 682 Percentage of EPA in each of the lipidic classes (wt% with respect to the total EPA in the
 683 biomass). Data are shown as mean \pm SD, n = 3. When bars do not appear, standard deviations
 684 are smaller than the symbols.

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687 *Figure 3. SL extraction from *Nannochloropsis sp.* lyophilized biomass using hexane and from*
 688 *residual biomass (previously extracted with hexane) using ethanol. (A) ■ NSL, ▣ GL and □ PL*
 689 *content (wt% with respect to total SLs) of original biomass and of the different hexanic and*
 690 *ethanolic extracts obtained under different operational conditions (Experiments 2 and 6, Table*
 691 *3). (B) ■ NSL, ▣ GL, □ PL and ▨ EPA yield (wt% with respect to the total contained in the*
 692 *original biomass) in the previously indicated hexanic and ethanolic extracts. Data are shown as*
 693 *mean ± SD, n = 2. When bars do not appear, standard deviations are smaller than the symbols.*
 694 *a, b, c, d show significant differences in lipidic class content and lipid yield between extracts or*
 695 *experiments with a different letter ($\alpha = 0.05$).*

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699 *Figure 4.* Comparison between the simultaneous extraction and fractionation of microalgal
 700 lipids from *Nannochloropsis* sp. lyophilized and wet biomass in two steps using hexane and
 701 ethanol. (A) ■ NSL, ▣ GL and □ PL content (wt% with respect to the total SLs) of the original
 702 biomass and the hexanic and ethanolic extracts obtained from lyophilized biomass (Experiment
 703 11, Table 3) and from wet biomass (86 wt% water) obtained under the same operational

704 conditions (40 °C, 20 h and using 10 mL of solvent/g equivalent dry biomass). (B) ■ NSL, ▣
705 GL, □ PL and ▣ EPA yield (wt% with respect to the total contained in the original biomass) in
706 previously indicated hexanic and ethanolic extracts. Data are shown as mean \pm SD, n = 2. When
707 bars do not appear, standard deviations are smaller than the symbols. ^{a, b, c, d} show significant
708 differences in lipidic class content and lipid yield between extracts or experiments with a
709 different letter ($\alpha = 0.05$).

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